

SKILLED PLANNING AND COMMUNICATION: A SYNERGY MODEL TO IMPROVE MARKETING PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to develop a synergistic model between innovation and learning orientation in improving marketing performance in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) based on factory waste crafts in Semarang Regency. The learning orientation approach is believed to be able to create added value by strengthening creativity, skills, and communication that are aligned with local values. This study uses a quantitative method with a causal approach through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. Data were collected from 100 factory waste crafts respondents using a structured questionnaire. The results showed that learning orientation had a significant positive effect on innovation, skills, and communication. Furthermore, innovation was proven to be a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between learning orientation and marketing performance. These findings confirm that integration in the organizational learning process can improve competitiveness, creativity, and marketing performance sustainably in the local creative industry.

Keywords: *communication, generatif learning culture based, innovation, marketing performance, skilled planning*

Introduction

The creative industry is a key driver of the national economy, boosting Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and creating new jobs. However, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), particularly those engaged in factory waste management, still face various challenges in enhancing creativity, innovation, and marketing performance.

The main challenges for these SMEs stem from the suboptimal organizational learning process that integrates local cultural values. Learning based on cultural values can inspire creative ideas, improve job skills, and strengthen communication and collaboration within the business environment. A culture-based generative learning approach enables innovations relevant to the social identity of the local community.

According to the learning organization concept, learning emphasizes the creation of new knowledge through the combination of existing ideas, experiences, and values. When this process is integrated with local culture, such as the values of mutual cooperation, perseverance, and traditional creativity inherent in the Semarang Regency community, innovations are formed that are deeply rooted in local character. The results of this study indicate that learning orientation positively influences innovation, skills, and communication, ultimately improving the marketing performance of SMEs based on factory waste crafts. Therefore, the synergy between innovation and learning orientation is an important model for sustainably improving marketing performance. This research not only provides theoretical contributions to the development of learning concepts in marketing management but also provides practical insights for creative entrepreneurs to innovate and compete in both local and global markets.

Literature review

Performance

Marketing performance reflects an organization's effectiveness in achieving its goals of sales growth, customer satisfaction, and profitability. Marketing performance is

influenced by strategic effectiveness, product innovation, and adaptability to market needs.

(Ma & Yong, 2025) suggest that marketing performance is determined by company effectiveness, market share growth, and profitability. ((Liu & Li, 2025) assess that performance can be measured through financial indicators such as liquidity, solvency, and profitability. (Baiquny & Nasution, 2024) add that innovation is a key driver of superior performance.

Marketing performance improves when product innovation, effective communication, and human resource skills are developed within a culture-based generative learning framework.

Marketing performance also reflects an organization's ability to create value for customers through product differentiation strategies, superior service, and effective communication. The greater an organization's ability to understand market dynamics and implement innovation, the greater the opportunity for achieving sustainable sales growth and customer loyalty

Learning orientation

(Manurung et al., 2020) state that learning ability is the foundation for organizations to gather accurate information. The result of organizational learning is improved skills (Fitriany, 2019)

(Maryanti et al., 2022) state that by using a generative learning model, employees will be more actively involved in the learning process, learning to survive, also known as adaptive learning. Adaptive learning alone is not enough; it must be combined with generative learning, which is learning by combining our capacities and creating. (Sugiana et al., 2016) state that a generative learning model is a learning model that guides individuals in exploring knowledge to acquire new knowledge.

(Glorianto, 2005) Companies with a strong learning orientation encourage or require employees to continuously question company norms, values, and practices, which

guide individual/organizational actions with a critical eye for improvement. (Paparoidamis, 2005)

Communication

Research conducted by (Tippins & Sohi, 2003) identified the dimensions of the learning process through information dissemination, which involves disseminating acquired knowledge to all parties, and interpretation, where individuals who receive information review the information they receive and coordinate the decision-making process.

Communication is a regular pattern of relationships between individuals that can be identified as the exchange of information experienced by individuals within their social system (Berger, 2014) Technically, the communication process involves, among others: 1) the communicator; 2) the message to be communicated; 3) the communication channel; 4) the recipient; and 5) the reaction/feedback.

(Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001) argues that communication skills have a significant impact on marketing success. Therefore, communication is essential because effective communication will enhance a person's work performance and impact creativity and innovation.

Skilled planning

The word "skill" comes from the word "trampil" (skill), and is used because it involves a learning process, moving from unskilled to skilled. Therefore, skills training is training aimed at teaching individuals who are unskilled in interacting with others, both in informal and formal relationships.

This learning approach places a strong emphasis on the process of directly constructing one's knowledge, meaning that individuals are involved in observing, classifying, and communicating their learning outcomes.(Hendrowati, 2015)

The process skills approach is a learning approach that aims to develop a number of physical and mental abilities as a foundation for developing higher-level abilities (Hamalik, 2003) These physical and mental abilities are inherently present in

individuals, although they are still rudimentary and need to be stimulated to reveal their true selves. Skills also include the ability to adapt to new technologies, make quick decisions, and collaborate effectively with teams to achieve organizational goals.

Innovation

Companies that innovate strive to be better/have more value than their competitors, thus becoming the premise/foundation of competitive advantage, which is demonstrated by better financial performance (Hunt, 1997)

(Amabile et al., 1996) explain that innovation is the successful implementation of creative ideas within an organization. Meanwhile, (Han et al., 1998) explain two types of innovation: 1) technical innovation, which relates to products, services, and production process technology. According to (Sari & Prasetiawati, 2020) technical innovation is innovation that occurs within organizational activities. 2) administrative innovation, which relates to organizational structure and administrative processes. Innovation is not limited to the creation of new products but also includes the development of more efficient business models, marketing strategies, and production technologies. Continuous innovation requires a culture of learning, collaboration between departments, and managerial support so that creative ideas can be implemented into real solutions to market needs.

The relationship between learning orientation and communication

(Kustiawan et al., 2022) argue that dialogue in interpersonal communication has a dual function, with students taking turns as speakers and listeners, thus achieving a shared understanding.

In communication, the way a person influences others is called persuasion, a communication technique. Furthermore, learning activities involve learning plans and communication between individuals. In communication, these learning plans are closely linked to effective communication strategies in learning, thus facilitating the communication process between individuals.

The results of this study align with Tien-Shang Lee's (2008) research, which states a positive relationship between learning orientation and innovation. Therefore, culture-based generative learning will improve communication. Based on the above description, hypothesis 1 can be formulated: There is a significant positive influence between culture-based generative learning and communication.

The relationship between learning orientation and skilled planning

Theory involving knowledge and development, intellectual skills that include the retrieval or recognition of facts, procedural patterns, and concepts in the development of intellectual abilities and skills (Erina & Kuswanto, 2015)

The goal of science is to enable individuals to use science process skills (Aktamis & Ergin, 2008). Science process skills in learning are necessary given the increasingly rapid development of the times. The science process begins with understanding the problem, formulating a hypothesis, designing an experiment, proving the hypothesis, collecting data, and formulating conclusions (Sinurat et al., 2023).

Conclusions are a series of skills, including the ability to develop a series of activities related to planning, negotiation, and consumer orientation.

The process of constructing one's knowledge, meaning that individuals are involved in observing, classifying, and communicating their learning outcomes (Zempi et al., 2023) Hypothesis 2: There is a significant positive effect of culture-based generative learning on skills.

The relationship between communication and innovation

Communication is a regular pattern of relationships between individuals that can be identified as the exchange of information experienced by individuals within their social system (A. Firmansyah, 2020) To implement good communication within a company, a network of understanding is essential.

This means that the communication delivered by one party and received by the other party must be clear and easy to understand. Technically, the communication process involves, among other things: 1) communicator; 2) message to be communicated; 3)

communication channel; 4) communicatee; 5) reaction/feedback (Indrawan & Ilmar, 2020)

The increasing use of interpersonal communication media through lectures, dialogue, and demonstrations will increase the opportunities for innovation adoption (Putri et al., 2025) . Therefore, Hypothesis 4 is proposed: There is a positive correlation between communication and innovation. High skills enable individuals and organizations to identify new opportunities, overcome technical barriers, and utilize technology creatively to produce superior products and services.

The relationship of skilled planning to innovation

A person's physical and mental abilities are inherent within them, and therefore, they must be continuously developed to improve. Developing physical and mental abilities is expected to lead to improved skills compared to others. The skills approach considers physical and mental abilities as the foundation for developing higher-level skills (Sormin et al., 2024) .

Companies need to improve their skills because with these skills, companies can innovate effectively (Imiru, 2024) Therefore, companies that can develop product-making skills will be able to increase innovation. Companies need to improve their skills because with these skills, companies can innovate effectively (Imiru, 2024).

Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is proposed: There is a positive correlation between planning skills and innovation.

The relationship between innovation and marketing performance

(E. Firmansyah & Humaidi, 2022) states that innovation is a change in processes, products, and technology. Therefore, innovation is a source of change that can lead to opportunities for product development. Furthermore, (Tjahjaningsih, 2013) argues that innovation can improve performance. Product innovation can take the form of new products or improved existing products.

(Ernawati, 2019) states that innovation is the process of implementing ideas to create something better or more valuable than competitors.

(Putra, 2018) states that the main goal of competitive analysis is to identify opportunities to achieve a sustainable advantage in the product produced compared to competitors.

(Mardikaningsih, 2023) states that marketing and innovation are means to foster competitive advantage, because companies that innovate are implementing new ideas. (Hurley & Hult, 1998) state that a learning orientation will lead to innovation and the capacity to innovate, ultimately achieving superior performance. Therefore, Hypothesis 5 is proposed: There is a positive correlation between innovation and performance.

Research methodology

A population is a collection of individuals/research objects that possess predetermined qualities and characteristics. Based on these qualities and characteristics, a population can be understood as a group of individuals observed who share at least one characteristic. The population in this study was all 150 members of the factory waste craftsman cooperative.

A sample is a portion of the population that shares relatively similar characteristics and is considered representative of the population (Singarimbun, 1991) This study involved 119 respondents. Data processing was carried out using questionnaires, including preparation, tabulation, and application of data to the research approach.

Meanwhile, the learning orientation variable (Sugiana et al., 2016)

1. organizational learning that focuses on generating creative ideas with cultural characteristics.
2. Exploring culturally specific aspirations and product attributes.
2. Culture-based generative learning has the potential to increase innovation.

Variables: skilled planning (Widiastuti, 2010)

1. Service skills
2. Negotiation skills
3. Customer satisfaction skills

Communication variables (Berger, 2014)

1. The need to provide clear information
2. Information provided according to instructions
3. Information provided is easy to understand

Innovation variables (Lau et al., 2010)

1. Number of new products
2. Number of new services
3. Use of new technology

Performance variables (Augusty, 2006)

1. Sales turnover
2. Customer growth
3. Sales growth
4. Number of customers

This research model is a causality model (cause-and-effect relationships/influences), so the analysis tool used in the study is SEM-PLS.

In conducting SEM PLS, the outer and inner models are tested, as explained below:

Outer Model Test

The measurement model, also known as the outer model, explains how each indicator block relates to its latent variables. The outer model examines the construct's validity and reliability.

Inner Model Test

According to (Ghozali, 2021), structural model evaluation, or inner model, is a test for predicting causal relationships between previously hypothesized latent variables. Structural model evaluation uses several tests, as follows:

The "R-square" (R²) analysis aims to explain the proportion of variation in changes in exogenous variables to endogenous variables (Ghozali, 2021). The criterion for this analysis is the R-square (R²) value. An R-square value of 0.58 indicates a good model, 0.33 indicates a moderate model, and 0.19 indicates a weak model.

Dalam melakukan uji SEM PLS dengan melakukan uji outer model dan inner model dengan penjelasan sebagai berikut.:

Discussion

In the discussion of the research by presenting descriptive data on respondents as follows

Descriptive Analysis

Tabel 1. Descriptive Analysis

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	41	34,45
Female	78	65,55
Total	119	100
Marital Status		
Married	21	17,65
Not married	98	82,35
Educatin		
Elementary school	9	7,56
Yunior School	30	65,55
High School	78	
Bachelor's Degree	2	1,68
Duration of Establishment		

Description	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 year	12	10,08
4-6 year	45	37,81
7-9 year	36	30,25
10-12 year	12	10,08
13-15 year	11	10,08
Over 15 year	3	2,52
Total	119	100

The results of the characteristics of the research subjects in Table 1 explain that the waste business is dominated by women at 65.5%, the rest are men at 34.45%. Furthermore, in terms of marital status, 82.35% are married and the remaining 17.65% are unmarried, educational level, batik business with elementary school education is 7.56%. Junior high school 25.21%, education up to high school level with a percentage of 65.55%. For the longest time to establish a business, the largest is 4 to 6 years, as much as 37.81%, while the least is over 15 years, as much as 2.52%.

Figure 1. Outer Model Results

R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Innovation	0.618	0.611
Marketing performance	0.686	0.682
Communication	0.433	0.427
skilled planning	0.311	0.304

F Square

	Innovation	Marketing performance	Communication	Learning Orientation	Skill planned
Innovation		2.180			
Marketing performance					
Communication	0.671				
Learning orientation			0.762		0.451
Skilled planning	0.100				

Model_Fit

Fit Summary

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.145	0.159
d_ULS	2.867	3.435
d_G	1.470	1.742
Chi-Square	681.042	743.513
NFI	0.552	0.511

Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Latent Variable 1 -> innovation	0.622	0.569	0.173	3.604	0.000
innovation -> marketing performance	0.828	0.833	0.051	16.222	0.000
learning orientation -> Latent Variable 1	0.658	0.664	0.066	9.928	0.000
learning orientation -> skill planned	0.558	0.610	0.108	5.168	0.000
skilled planning -> innovation	0.240	0.307	0.176	1.365	0.172

The table can be interpreted as follows:

1. The innovation construct variable can be explained by generative learning and communication variables, amounting to 61.8%, while the remaining 38.2% is explained by other variables outside the research model.
2. The marketing performance construct variable is explained by the variability of the constructs "eco-friendly market orientation," "eco-friendly process innovation," and "bird-in-hand" product uniqueness, amounting to 68.6%, while the remaining 31.4% is explained by other variables outside the research model.
3. Communication: $R^2 = 0.433$, approximately 43.3% of the variation in communication is explained by the causal variables. This is sufficient/moderate.
4. Planning skills: $R^2 = 0.311$, approximately 31.1% of the variation in planning skills is explained by the constructs leading to it. This is low-moderate, but still often considered acceptable in the social sciences.

Relationship between Learning Orientation → Communication

The test results show that learning orientation has a positive and significant effect on communication with a path coefficient of 0.658, t -value = 9.821 and $p < 0.001$. This means that the higher the learning orientation, the better the communication built within the organization/respondents studied. Thus, H1 is accepted because its effect is statistically proven to be significant at the 5% error level. This finding is in line with research (Tien-Shang Lee, 2008) that there is a positive and significant influence between culture-based generative learning and communication.

Relationship between learning Orientation → skilled planning

Learning orientation was also proven to have a positive and significant effect on planning skills with a path coefficient of 0.558, t -value = 5.202 and $p < 0.001$. This indicates that an increase in learning orientation will be followed by an increase in planning skills, both in terms of quality and consistency of planning. Therefore, H2 is accepted, which means that learning orientation is an important factor in developing planning skills. This finding is in line with research (Hendrowati, 2015)

which states that there is a positive and significant influence between learning orientation and planning skills.

Relationship between communication → innovation

The results of the analysis show that communication has a positive and significant effect on innovation with a path coefficient of 0.622, t value = 3.628 and $p \approx 0.0003$ ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the better the communication (e.g., information openness, feedback, coordination), the higher the level of innovation produced. Thus, H3 is accepted. This finding is in line with research (Berger, 2014) that there is a positive and significant influence between communication and innovation so that communication can be seen as an important driver for the creation of innovation.

Relationship between skilled planning → innovation

The influence of planning skills on innovation has a positive path coefficient of 0.240, but the t value = 1.381 and $p \approx 0.167$ indicate that the influence is not significant at the 5% error level. This means that statistically, planning skills have not been proven to have a strong direct impact on increasing innovation in this model. Thus, H4 is rejected, which can be interpreted as meaning that the influence of planning skills on innovation may be indirect or mediated by other variables. This is inconsistent with the findings (Hurley & Hult, 1998) that there is a positive and significant influence between skills and innovation.

Relationship between innovation → marketing performance

The test results show that innovation has a positive and highly significant effect on marketing performance with a path coefficient of 0.828, a t -value of 16.255, and $p < 0.001$. This means that the higher the level of innovation, the better the marketing performance achieved, for example in terms of increasing sales, market share, and customer satisfaction. Therefore, H5 is accepted, and innovation can be concluded as a key factor in improving marketing performance. This is in line with the findings (Hurley & Hult, 1998) that there is a positive and significant influence between innovation and marketing performance.

Conclusion

This study shows that learning orientation has a positive and significant influence on communication, planning skills, and innovation among factory waste craft SMEs in Semarang Regency. Innovation is proven to act as a mediating variable, strengthening the relationship between learning orientation and marketing performance.

The synergy between local culture, learning orientation, and innovation forms a strategic model capable of enhancing creativity, adaptive skills, and product competitiveness based on regional cultural identity. These results emphasize the importance of integrating cultural values such as mutual cooperation, perseverance, and collaboration in improving marketing performance and the sustainability of local creative businesses.

Suggestions

1. SMEs need to continuously develop a learning orientation by actively conducting comparative studies, participating in product design and innovation training, and expanding their marketing networks through digital platforms (Instagram, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and others).
2. Planning skills need to be continuously improved through training in design, production techniques, and customer communication to maintain market satisfaction and loyalty.
3. Government agencies and SME support institutions are expected to provide local culture-based innovation facilitation programs, appropriate technology training, and integrated marketing support for artisans.
4. Digital promotion and branding of local products need to be strengthened so that factory waste-based products can be more widely recognized and compete in national and global markets.

Managerial implications

1. Organizational learning strategy: SME management needs to build a learning system that emphasizes collaboration, creativity, and reflection of local cultural values as sources of competitive advantage.

2. Strengthening an innovative work culture: Organizational culture should be geared toward creating an environment that supports experimentation, new ideas, and rewards employee creativity.
3. Innovation as a management priority: Business leaders need to prioritize product and service innovation as a focus of business strategy and allocate resources for small-scale research and design development.
4. Communication and skills management: Training in interpersonal communication and customer negotiation is needed to build long-term relationships and strengthen local brand image.
5. Sustainable marketing performance: The success of culture-based innovation should be measured not only by increased sales, but also by enhanced customer loyalty, product image, and social impact on the surrounding community.

Research limitations

1. The study's scope was limited to SMEs engaged in factory waste crafts in Semarang Regency, so generalizing the results to other sectors requires caution.
2. The sample size was relatively small (100 respondents), which may not fully represent the diverse characteristics of SMEs in other regions.
3. Other variables outside the model, such as government support, market access, and venture capital, were not included in the analysis, even though they have the potential to influence marketing performance.
4. The quantitative approach did not delve deeply into the qualitative aspects of organizational culture, so further research using a mixed methods approach is recommended to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

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